

THE EFFECT OF COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE AND KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN REDUCING UNEMPLOYMENT IN THE DEPARTEMENT TENAGA KERJA AND TRANSMIGRASI REGENCY SERANG

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the correlation between collaborative governance, knowledge management and their effect both partially and simultaneously on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Serang Regency. This study uses a quantitative approach aimed at testing hypotheses. The population and sample in this study were all employees of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency and Vocational High Schools in Serang Regency with a total of 221. The data analysis technique was using the multivariate data analysis method using SEM (Structural Equation Modeling). The results show that partially collaborative governance has a very low and insignificant effect on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Serang Regency, with a coefficient value of -0.05. Meanwhile, knowledge management has been partially proven to have a significant and significant effect on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency with a coefficient value of 0.51. Meanwhile, collaborative governance and knowledge management have been shown to have an effect on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency with a coefficient of determination of 0.25. This study also produced new findings, namely the basis or trigger of the concept of knowledge management which was not mentioned by the theory proposed by Fernandez & Saberwal, namely absorptive capacity. As well as a new dimension that was born by the concept of collaborative governance in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency, namely actor behavior.

Keywords: collaborative governance, knowledge management, work productivity

1. INTRODUCTION

Human development is one of the ways to improve the quality of education, namely increasing the quality of education output in each workforce. A good quality workforce can encourage and increase the absorption of the workforce in the world of work. Article 27 Paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution has mandated that every citizen has the right to work and a decent living for humanity. This means that the state must have an obligation to provide jobs for job seekers and a decent living for citizens whose socio-economic status is still low. While the people have the right to demand the government to provide jobs and provide a decent living. In an effort to achieve development goals, it cannot be done only by one party,

every component in the government must be actively involved. The concept of cooperation between government component institutions is called collaborative governance.

Institutional collaboration through collaborative governance is sought to solve the problem of employment and unemployment in Indonesia because almost all regions in Indonesia experience the same problems in the field of employment such as unemployment, especially educated unemployment.

According to data from the Central Statistics Agency, the highest national unemployment rate was contributed by Banten Province. Banten Province contributes 8.11% to the total number of Open Unemployment in Indonesia which is the first rank of the highest unemployment rate in Indonesia. Despite a declining trend, in the last year (2018-2019) the number of unemployed in Banten Province decreased by 6,947 people, in line with the open unemployment rate (TPT) which fell to 7.58 percent in February 2019. This condition is a big question mark, because as is known Banten Province is one of the buffer zones for the capital city with a fairly high industry, according to regulations, the Banten Provincial Government has set of rules that should support unemployment alleviation efforts, for example Banten Governor Regulation No. 9 of 2018 concerning Procedures for Submitting Job Vacancies and Employment Information where one of the points in the article states that people can work with their competencies and companies can recruit and place workers according to their area of expertise.

The open unemployment rate in Banten Province is occupied by Serang Regency, which is 10.65%, followed by Cilegon City, 9.68 percent, Tangerang Regency, 8.91 percent, Pandeglang Regency 8.71 percent, Serang City. , 8.08 percent, Lebak Regency, 8.05 percent, Tangerang City, 7.13 percent, and South Tangerang City, 4.79 percent. (BPS Banten Province, November 2019). Serang Regency as one of the industrial centers in Banten Province, actually recorded the highest unemployment rate in Banten Province, this should also be a concern.

Serang Regency is an area in Banten Province which bears the title as a contributor to the highest unemployment rate in Banten Province since 2012, and can only be separated from this predicate in 2020.

Picture. 1: Graph of Unemployment Rate in Serang Regency

Source: BPS Kab. Attack (2020)

The problem of unemployment is complex and complicated, requiring a serious and integrated solution. Unemployment alleviation cannot be carried out by the relevant agencies alone.

Collaboration between government components is allegedly the right solution that will reduce the unemployment rate in Serang Regency, and the process will become even more optimal with good and optimal knowledge management. As found in previous research, the dimensions in knowledge management have a positive effect on work productivity (Torabi & El Den, 2017: 308)

Solving the problem of alleviating unemployment in Seang Regency has so far been carried out individually by government agencies that have an interest. The Department of Manpower and Transmigration has its own program, the Department of Education has its own program, the Department of Industry has its own program, while the problem of unemployment is a common problem that must be solved in an integrated and comprehensive manner.

To uncover the constraints and obstacles in this research, observation and dialogue with several policy implementers at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency, then the results reveal that productivity has not been in line with expectations, which is indicated by the following problems:

- 1) Work efficiency, this can be seen from the achievement of a clear Standard Operational Procedure (SOP) and in the implementation of unemployment alleviation programs carried out by the Office of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency.
- 2) Work productivity, this can be seen from the analysis of the process which also involves the resources and time used in completing the work.
- 3) Work quality. The achievement target for alleviating unemployment which is expected to occur through the program of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency has not found the level of achievement that is in accordance with the expected performance target.

The strengthening of the three problems as a result of the initial research is stated in the recapitulation table report the work productivity of the unemployment alleviation policy in Serang Regency by the Department of Manpower and Transmigration is as follows:

Activity	Target	Reality	Information
Entrepreneurship training for working age group	Conducted at least 2x training in each district	Not all sub-districts have implemented entrepreneurship training	Not on target
Implementation of MoU with companies around Serang Regency	100% of companies cooperate with the DisnakertransKab. Attack for job placement	According to data up to 2020, 55% of companies that have signed the MoU	Not on target. One of the reasons is because it is entering a pandemic period.
Decrease in unemployment	Below 5%	Still around 12.22%	Although it decreased from the previous year, the decrease was not significant

Table 1: Work Productivity Report Recapitulation

Based on the research background, the research problem is formulated as follows:

1. How big is the influence of collaborative governance which is determined by the context of the system, drivers, dynamics of collaboration, collaborative action and adaptation to work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency?
2. How big is the influence of knowledge management which is determined by knowledge discovery, knowledge capture, knowledge sharing, and knowledge application on the work productivity of alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency?
3. How much influence does collaborative governance and knowledge management have simultaneously on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency?

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

Collaborative Governance

Ansell and Gash (2007: 543) state that collaborative governance is a new strategy in governance that makes various policy makers gather in the same forum to create a common consensus. Furthermore, Ansell and Gash define collaborative governance as an arrangement of governance in which one or more public institutions directly involve non-governmental actors in a formal, consensus-oriented, consultative collective policy-making process with the aim of making or implementing public policies, managing programs or public assets.

Collaborative governance is one of the concepts and scientific developments of Governance. Governance itself has a very diverse and broad meaning. Basically, governance is the act of governing or the act of governing. This means that governance is the act of regulating; in various contexts and in various ways. Howlett & Ramesh (2014: 318) states that governing is: “what governments do: controlling the allocation of resources among social actors; providing a set of rules and operating a set of institutions setting out ‘who gets what, where, when, and how’ in society.” In this context, governance relates to how to organize and allocate resources among various social factors, including a set of rules and institutions so that they can determine 'who gets what, where and how' in social life.

As part of governance, Collaborative governance emphasizes the importance of collaboration between various actors and parties in the development and governance process.

There are six characteristics of collaborative governance according to Anshel& Gash (2007), namely First, the forum is initiated by a public institution. Second, participants in the forum should include non-governmental actors. Third, participants must be directly involved in policy making and not merely “consult” with the government. Fourth, the forum must be formally organized and have regular meetings. Fifth, the policies taken must be based on consensus. And sixth, collaboration focuses on public policy or public management. Based on character from this, it can be seen that collaborative governance must consist of government and non-government elements, each party must play an active role and have balanced interests.

De Seve (2009: 135-136) states that there are several important items that can be used to measure the success of a network or collaboration in governance, including: Networked structure.

- a. Commitmen to a common purpose
- b. Trust among the participants
- c. Governance, a process of interaction and reciprocal relations carried out by the Government and its citizens.
- d. Access to authority
- e. Distributive accountability / responsibility
- f. Information sharing
- g. Access to resources.

In this study, the collaboration process theory was chosen from Emerson, Nabatchi, & Balogh (2012), because it saw a comprehensive and appropriate component used in answering the problem.

Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is the process of creating, sharing, using, and managing the knowledge and information of an organization. Knowledge in the organization comes from the knowledge of the individual individuals in it. Knowledge resides in the minds of individuals and only when it is articulated and shared becomes encoded in organizational

processes, documents, products, services, facilities and systems provided the individual has the intention to share what is known. (Torabi, 2017:301).

Individual knowledge consists of intangible awareness, learned facts and information which are manifested as ideas, judgments, talents, root causes, relationships, perspectives and concepts (Kovačič, 2006:53-66). Furthermore, knowledge creation and transmission is seen as strategically important as one of the fundamental processes that determine organizational learning and innovation capabilities. (Salmador, 2007:367). Knowledge creation is an integral part, because knowledge is the one of them sustainable competitive advantage that is the result of learning. Knowledge transmission is the acquisition of knowledge in an organization that is disseminated by individuals to other individuals. The Knowledge Management cycle involves both the creation and acquisition of organizational knowledge. Knowledge creation involves developing new knowledge or replacing existing knowledge with new content. (Nonaka, 1994:14-37).

According to Chen et al (2010), emphasizing that knowledge management is a process of human activity related to knowledge, but does not deal with the special nature of various types of knowledge, or the relative importance of different knowledge in an organization. Various studies have shown that knowledge management is positively related to the success of an organization, especially in manufacturing companies (Gregory, et al, 2010).

Knowledge Management is carried out in a knowledge management system, or Knowledge Management System. Most organizations that implement KMS use a three-pronged approach to manage it, namely people (people), process (process) and technology (technology).

Knowledge can be categorized into two types, namely tacit and explicit (Chen & Shu, 2010:217). As also stated by Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995). Polanyi (1958) states that explicit knowledge refers to structural knowledge expressed by text, images and symbols, which can be taught orally and learned by textbooks, reference materials, databases, while tacit knowledge exists only in people's minds, which is difficult to express in words. -words, symbols, media images. In an organization, explicit knowledge is not a problem because it is easy to document, archive, and code. On the other hand, tacit knowledge is a challenge in itself because knowledge is often perceived as very valuable to be shared and used in the right way.

Knowledge management is said to be successful if it can apply a series of approaches to organizational knowledge, including: accumulation, use, distribution, and ownership. (Kongpichayanond, 2009:375) Thus, knowledge management can be seen as a strategy that helps organizations use knowledge to envision, create and control the entire decision-making process.

Becerra-Fernandez and Sabherwal (2010), suggested four dimensions of knowledge management in organizations, namely knowledge discovery, knowledge capture, knowledge sharing and knowledge application.

Work productivity

Productivity is a combination of accuracy and optimal use of available labor and material resources and efficiency is determined through performance. (Tavari, et al, 2008: 102). Efficiency and productivity are two important components of productivity and are usually influenced by various factors. Simply put, productivity is expressed by the ratio of output to input as a fraction. But productivity in organizations is a coordinated and planned series of actions to improve programs and make better use of talent, facilities, space, and places.

Productivity implies a mental attitude that always has the view "the quality of life today must be better than yesterday, and tomorrow is better than today". Productive mental attitudes include, among others, motivational, disciplined, creative, innovative, dynamic, professional and fighting spirit. (Sedarmayanti, 2009). The dimensions for measuring productivity in this study are efficiency, productivity and quality. (Robbins, 2013).

1. Productivity, namely the level of use of human resources, the organization is maximized with the intention of increasing profits or reducing losses from each unit in the use of resources.
2. Efficiency, namely the level of an activity completed at the desired initial time, viewed from the point of coordination with the output and maximizing the time available for work activities
3. Quality is the quality of work measured from the employee's perception of the quality of the work produced and the perfection of the task on the skills and abilities of employees.

Framework of thinking

Figure 2 Research Framework

Hypothesis

Based on the description above, the following research hypotheses can be developed:

- 1) Collaborative governance which is determined by the context of the system, drivers, collaboration dynamics, collaboration and adaptation actions have a significant effect on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Serang Regency.
- 2) Knowledge management determined by knowledge discovery, knowledge capture, knowledge sharing, and knowledge application has a significant effect on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Serang Regency.
- 3) Collaborative governance and knowledge management simultaneously affect work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Serang Regency

3. METHOD

This research is a research with a quantitative approach that aims to test the hypothesis. According to Sugiyono (2013:13) quantitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine certain populations or samples, retrieval technique the sample is generally done randomly

The population and sample in this study were all employees of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency and Vocational High Schools in Serang Regency with a total of 221. The data analysis technique was using the multivariate data analysis method using SEM (Structural Equation Modeling).

4. RESEARCH RESULT

1. Description of Research Object

The unit of analysis in this study is the Office of Manpower and Transmigration in Serang Regency, the Office of Education and Culture and Vocational High Schools in Serang Regency, represented by the Special Job Exchange Unit. The population is all employees of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Serang Regency, as many as 27 people, Principals of Vocational High Schools in Serang Regency as many as 97 people and the Special Job Exchange Unit for Vocational High Schools as many as 97 people.

From the total population, the entire population is used as a sample, because the sample in this study was determined using non-probability sampling with a saturated sampling technique. Questionnaires were distributed using the Jot Form and Google Form application facilities, which were sent via WhatsApp communication messages and e-mail as well as direct questionnaires to respondents.

Respondents by gender. Based on the table above, the majority of respondents are male, amounting to 154 people (69.7%) while the female sex is 67 people (30.3%).

Meanwhile, based on the age range, the majority of respondents are in the age range of 25-34 years, which is 107 people (48.4%), those aged 35-49 years are 66 people (29.9%), aged 15-24 years are 43 people (19.5%), and those who aged 50-64 years amounted to 5 people (2.3%).

Validity and Reliability Test Results

Testing content validity (content validity) through a test tool commonly used with correlation testing is the Product Moment Model Karl Pearson (Hair, et.al, 2010) which is stated in the statistical formula formula as follows:

$$r = \frac{n\sum XY - (\sum X \cdot \sum Y)}{\sqrt{n\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} \cdot \sqrt{n\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2}}$$

1. Collaborative Governance Variable Validity Test (X1)

Item	R	R-TabLE	Decision
1	0.452	0.132	Valid
2	0.522	0.132	Valid
3	0.505	0.132	Valid
4	0.522	0.132	Valid
5	0.569	0.132	Valid
6	0.510	0.132	Valid
7	0.529	0.132	Valid
8	0.545	0.132	Valid
9	0.552	0.132	Valid
10	0.500	0.132	Valid
11	0.448	0.132	Valid
12	0.396	0.132	Valid
13	0.565	0.132	Valid
14	0.533	0.132	Valid
15	0.487	0.132	Valid

Table 2 X1 . Variable Validity Test

2. Knowledge Management Variable Validity Test Results (X2)

Item	R	R-Table	Decision
16	0.596	0.132	Valid
17	0.630	0.132	Valid
18	0.658	0.132	Valid
19	0.369	0.132	Valid
20	0.442	0.132	Valid
21	0.582	0.132	Valid
22	0.566	0.132	Valid
23	0.347	0.132	Valid
24	0.448	0.132	Valid
25	0.548	0.132	Valid
26	0.555	0.132	Valid
27	0.456	0.132	Valid

Table 3 X2 . Variable Validity Test

3. Work Productivity Variable Validity Test (Y)

Item	R	R-Table	Decision
28	0.640	0.132	Valid
29	0.700	0.132	Valid
30	0.598	0.132	Valid
31	0.634	0.132	Valid
32	0.623	0.132	Valid
33	0.445	0.132	Valid
34	0.501	0.132	Valid
35	0.421	0.132	Valid
36	0.519	0.132	Valid

Table 4 Variable Validity Test Y

4. Reliability Test

The reliability coefficient decisions of each variable are as presented in the table of reliability test results as follows:

Variable	Reliabilitas	Critical Point	decision
Collaborative Governance (X1)	0.891	0,6	Reliabel
Knowledge Management (X2)	0.791	0,6	Reliabel
Work Productivity (Y)	0.802	0,6	Reliabel

Table 5 Instrument Reliability Test Results

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

1. Statistik Deskriptif Variabel Collaborative Governance

Dimension	Item	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean/dimensi
System Context (X1.1)	1.	221	1	5	3.195	1.050	2.990
	2.	221	1	5	2.955	0.994	
	3.	221	1	5	2.887	0.920	
	4.	221	1	5	3.000	0.995	
	5.	221	1	5	2.914	1.043	
Drivers (X1.2)	6.	221	1	5	3.068	1.004	3.035
	7.	221	1	5	3.100	1.009	
	8.	221	1	5	3.109	0.913	
	9.	221	1	5	3.045	0.957	
	10.	221	1	5	2.855	0.985	
Dynamics of Collaboration (X1.3)	11.	221	2	5	3.579	0.667	3.383
	12.	221	1	5	3.213	0.961	
	13.	221	2	5	3.647	0.822	
	14.	221	1	5	3.122	0.830	
	15.	221	1	5	3.353	0.865	
Mean per variable							3.136

Table 6 Variable Descriptive Statistics X1

2. Knowledge Management Variable Descriptive Statistics (X2)

Dimension	Item	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean/dimensi
Knowledge Discovery (X2.1)	16	221	1	5	3.244	0.965	3.163
	17	221	1	5	2.982	0.929	
	18	221	1	5	3.262	0.931	
Knowledge capture (X2.2)	19	221	1	5	3.579	0.797	3.43
	20	221	1	5	3.14	1.042	
	21	221	1	5	3.57	0.843	
Knowledge sharing (X2.3)	22	221	1	5	3.783	0.779	3.51
	23	221	1	5	3.19	0.995	
	24	221	1	5	3.557	0.827	
Knowledge application (X2.4)	25	221	1	5	3.484	0.766	3.382
	26	221	1	5	3.131	1.034	
	27	221	1	5	3.529	0.834	
Mean per variable							3.371

Table 7 Descriptive Statistics of Variable X2

3. Descriptive Statistics of Work Productivity Variable (Y)

Dimensi	Item	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev	MeaN/dimensi
Efisien (Y ₁)	16	221	1	5	3.104	0.891	3.109
	17	221	1	5	3.118	0.951	
	18	221	1	5	3.104	0.881	
Efektif (Y ₂)	19	221	1	5	3.131	0.867	3.183
	20	221	1	5	3.344	0.792	
	21	221	1	5	3.072	0.866	
Kualitas (Y ₂)	22	221	1	5	3.579	0.842	3.486
	23	221	1	5	3.421	0.889	
	24	221	1	5	3.457	0.955	
Mean per variabel							3.259

Table 8 Descriptive Statistics Variable Y

Normality Check

Skewness			Kurtosis			Skewness and Kurtosis	
Value	Z-Score	P-Value	Value	Z-Score	P-Value	Chi-Square	P-Value
6.720	1.292	0.196	117.582	-0.615	0.539	2.048	0.359

Outlier Check

Variable	Skewness		Kurtosis		Skewness and Kurtosis	
	Z-Score	P-Value	Z-Score	P-Value	Chi-Square	P-Value
X1.1	-1.845	0.065	0.172	0.863	3.435	0.179
X1.2	-1.818	0.069	0.641	0.522	3.715	0.156
X1.3	-1.594	0.111	-1.046	0.295	3.634	0.163
X2.1	-1.857	0.063	-1.100	0.272	4.658	0.097
X2.2	0.302	0.763	0.117	0.907	0.105	0.949
X2.3	-0.564	0.573	-0.827	0.408	1.002	0.606
X2.4	-0.768	0.443	0.173	0.863	0.619	0.734
Y1	-1.671	0.095	-1.136	0.256	4.081	0.130
Y2	-0.249	0.803	-0.620	0.535	0.446	0.800
Y3	-1.494	0.135	1.411	0.158	4.223	0.121

Multicollinearity and Singularity Examination

Examination of the presence of multicollinearity and singularity in SEM analysis can be seen from the determinant value of the covariance matrix. The determinant of the sample covariance matrix which is small or close to zero is close to the presence of multicollinearity and singularity. From the calculation results, the determinant of the covariance matrix is 0.000004037228549583. Because the value is greater than zero, it indicates the absence of multicollinearity and singularity

Model Fit Test

Based on the structural model that has been made for the influence of collaborative governance variables and knowledge management variables on work productivity, here are some indices used to determine the suitability of the model in analysis of the structured equation model.

Size GFO	Target Match Rate	Estimated Results	Match Rate
Chi-square	Small value	36.03	Baik (Good fit)
P	$P > 0.05$	0.33	
NCP	Small value	3.03	Baik (Good fit)
Interval	Narrow intervals	0.0-21.65	
RMSEA	RMSEA \leq 0.08	0.021	Baik (Good fit)
P (close fit)	$P > 0.05$	0.91	
ECVI	Small value and close to ECVI saturated	M*= 0.37	Baik (Good fit)
		S*= 0.50	
		I*= 4.88	
AIC	Small value and close to AIC saturated	M*= 81.03	Baik (Good fit)
		S*= 110.00	
		I*= 1074.11	
CAIC	Small value and close to AIC saturated	M*= 182.19	Baik (Good fit)
		S*= 351.90	
		I*= 1118.09	
NFI	$NFI \geq 0.90$	0.97	Baik (Good fit)
NNFI	$NNFI \geq 0.90$	1	Baik (Good fit)
CFI	$CFI \geq 0.90$	1	Baik (Good fit)
IFI	$IFI \geq 0.90$	1	Baik (Good fit)
RFI	$RFI \geq 0.90$	0.95	Baik (Good fit)
CN	$CN \geq 200$	332.58	Baik (Good fit)
RMR	Standardized RMR \leq 0.05	0.04	Baik (Good fit)
GFI	$GFI \geq 0.90$	0.97	Baik (Good fit)
AGFI	$AGFI \geq 0.90$	0.95	Baik (Good fit)

Table 9 Evaluation of the Goodness of Fit Criteria

Measurement Model Analysis

The t-value of factor loading and standard factor loading of the observed variables on the latent variables in this study can be seen in the following table:

Ternama	Latent	Collaborative Governance (X1)		Knowledge Management (X2)		Work Productivity (Y)		Conclusion Validity
		SLF*	Nilai-t**	SLF*	Nilai-t**	SLF*	Nilai-t**	
X1.1		0.71	10.5					Good
X1.2		0.84	12.55					Good
X1.3		0.7	10.36					Good
X2.1				0.75	12.19			Good
X2.2				0.68	10.63			Good
X2.3				0.75	12.09			Good
X2.4				0.86	14.64			Good
Y1						0.79	11.13	Good
Y2						0.72	10.32	Good
Y3						0.65	9.39	good

Table 10 t-value, Standardized Factor Load, and Model Validity

Hasil perhitungan akhirdari CR dan VE dapat dilihat pada tabel sebagai berikut:

Variabel	CR	VE	Kesimpulan Reliabilitas
Collaborative Governance	0.796	0.567	Baik
Knowledge Management	0.847	0.582	Baik
Produktivitas Kerja	0.765	0.522	Baik

Tabel 10: CR, VE dan Reliabilitas Model

Structural Model Evaluation

The SEM and LISREL methods produce the estimated coefficient values and also the t-value for each coefficient.

The results of SEM in the influence structure that are tested based on the Standardized Solution and T-Value values can be seen in each of the following structural tests:

1. X1 Structure Test against Y

Figure 4 Standardized Solution Model Variable X1 against Y

Figure 5 Standardized Solution Model Variable X1 against Y

2. X2 Structure Test against Y

Figure 6 Standardized Solution Model Variable X2 against Y

Figure 7 Model T Value of Variable X2 to Y

3. Simultaneous Structure Test

Figure 8 Main Models of Standardized Solution

Figure 9 Main Model T-Value

Based on the picture above, the structural equations for the model are obtained as follows:

$$Y = -0.049 \cdot X_1 + 0.51 \cdot X_2, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.75, R^2 = 0.25$$

(0.078)	(0.084)	(0.14)
-0.62	6.05	5.36

1. The path coefficient of the variable X1 to Y is -0.049. The direction is negative, meaning that if X1 increases by 1 unit then Y will decrease by 0.049, and vice versa.
2. The path coefficient of the variable X2 to Y is 0.51. The direction is positive, meaning that if X2 increases by 1 unit then Y will increase by 0.51, and vice versa.
3. The value of R2 (R squared) obtained is 0.25. This means that X1 and X2 have an effect of 25.0% on Y

The results of the evaluation of the structural model of this research and its relationship to the research hypothesis are summarized in the following table:

Latent Variable	Observed Variables	A	γ	T-Value	R ²	Conclusion
X ₁	X _{1.1}	0.71		10.5	-	Proven as the right indicator
	X _{1.2}	0.84		12.55	-	Proven as the right indicator
	X _{1.3}	0.7		10.36	-	Proven as the right indicator
X ₂	X _{2.1}	0.75		12.19	-	Proven as the right indicator
	X _{2.2}	0.68		10.63	-	Proven as the right indicator
	X _{2.3}	0.75		12.09	-	Proven as the right indicator
	X _{2.4}	0.86		14.64	-	Proven as the right indicator
X ₁ → Y	-		-0,05	-0,62		Negative influence (Hypothesis 1 is rejected)
X ₂ → Y	-		0,51	6,05		Positive influence (Hypothesis 1 is accepted)
X ₁ dan X ₂ → Y	-				0.25	Influence simultaneously by 79% (Hypothesis 3 accepted)

Table 13 Structural Model Evaluation Recap Table

Research Findings

This study also produced new findings, namely the basis or trigger of the concept of knowledge management which was not mentioned by the theory proposed by Fernandez &Saberwal, namely absorptive capacity. As well as the new dimensions that were born by the concept of collaborative governance in alleviating the unemployment rate at the Department of Manpower and Human Resources Transmigration in Serang Regency, namely actor behavior.

5. Conclusion

1. Testing the first hypothesis shows that collaborative governance has a very low and insignificant effect on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Serang Regency.
2. Testing the second hypothesis shows that knowledge management has a positive and significant impact on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Serang Regency.
3. The results of testing the third hypothesis show that collaborative governance and knowledge management together on work productivity have a positive and significant effect on work productivity in alleviating unemployment at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Serang Regency.

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